

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Natural enemies of brown planthopper and green leafhopper in India

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Severe infestations of the rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix nigropictus* occurred in several localities in Mandya, Karnataka, during the summer (Jan.–May) and kharif (May–Dec.) paddy seasons of 1976. Hoppers at all growth stages were collected and separated into cages. The predators found in association with them were placed in cages with the hoppers and their feeding on them was observed. The natural enemies listed below were common to the BPH and GLH.

EGG PARASITES

- Hymenoptera
Trichogrammatidae *Oligosita* sp.

NYMPHAL/ADULT PARASITES

- Hymenoptera
Dryinidae *Echthrodelpfax fairchildii* Fallen
Haplogonatopus sp.

PREDATORS

- Coleoptera
Coccinellidae *Coccinella arcuata* F.
- Hemiptera
Anthocoridae *Amphiaraeus constrictus* Stal.
(*hulvscens* Walk.)
Miridae *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter
Tytthus parviceps Reuter
- Hymenoptera
Formicidae *Camponotus* sp. 1
Camponotus sp. 2
(*fulvomarginatus* group)

PATHOGEN

- Entomophthorales
Entomophthoraceae *Entomophthora* sp.
- Amphibia
Anura, Ranidae *Rana limnocaris limnocaris* Wieg.

A few individuals of three Scelionid species, *Baeus*, *Gryon*, and *Oxyscelio* sp.,

also emerged in the tubes containing portions of leafsheaths bearing BPH and GLH eggs, but their exact status will have to be confirmed. Three unidentified species of spiders were also common in rice fields.

C. lividipennis was the most important predator. The dryinids gave up to 51 %

Two nematode parasites of rice brown Planthopper in India

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Several natural enemies of the rice brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* have recently been reported in India.

While continuing the survey, the author recorded two more nematode species as parasites. Both belong to the genus *Hexameris* of the family *Mermithidae*.

One nematode was minute (about 0.50 mm long) and scarce; it was reared on only three planthopper adults. More than 100 juveniles emerged from a single host. The other nematode, a Mermithid, was fairly large and common. The parasitized host had a greatly distended abdomen (Fig. 1) and fell on the ground before the parasite emerged. Only one nematode emerged from a single host (Fig. 2). Fifteen freshly emerged juvenile nematodes had an average length of

parasitism of BPH. Studies on the bioecology of these natural enemies are in progress.

The authors are grateful to the Director, Commonwealth Institute of Entomology, London, for identification of the specimens.

1. A brown planthopper (brachypterous female) parasitized by a Mermithid.
2. The nematode that has just emerged from brown planthopper.

4.84 mm (range, 4.20 to 5.90 mm) and an average width of 0.308 mm (0.286 to 0.315 mm). The nematode was reared from both brachypterous and macropterous males and females, but field parasitism of brachypterous females was consistently higher than that of other forms (see table).

Parasitism of brown planthopper^a (BPH) by a Mermithid. Karnataka, India, 1977.

Month	BPH examined (no.)					Parasitism (%)				
	Females		Males		Total	Females		Males		Total
	BM		BM			BM	BM			
October (2nd half)	70	43	6	32	151	12.9	4.6	0	3.1	8.0
November	94	115	20	53	282	33.0	10.4	15.0	9.4	18.1
December (1st week)	15	25	0	20	60	33.3	12.0	0	10.0	16.7

^aB = Brachypterous form; m = macropterous form.

To estimate field parasitism by the nematode, weekly collections of BPH infesting paddy were made. About half of the BPH collected were dissected; the others were reared in the laboratory. The table shows parasitism.

This Mermithid was also reared from

field collected *Sogatella furcifera* and *Nephotettix nigropictus*.

The Mirid *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, an important predator of the BPH, was parasitized by another Mermithid which may represent a new genus. However, it was scarce.

The author is grateful to Dr. G. O. Poiner, Jr., Invertebrate Pathologist, University of California, Berkeley, California, U.S.A., for identifying the nematodes. Specific identification was not possible as only juvenile, no adult, nematodes were obtained.

Occurrence of brown planthopper on rice in West Bengal, India

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In West Bengal, the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* was first noted as a serious pest of summer (boro) rice in 1973 at Khanakul, Hooghly district. Epidemics of the pest have since appeared

regularly in ever-larger areas. Recently the infestation has spread to other rice-growing areas of West Bengal, particularly river and coastal belts. The BPH has also been recorded on main winter (kharif or aman) rice, but there damage is less.

The main rice-growing area of Khanakul is low-lying and basinlike; water from two rivers and a number of drainage channels are impounded there. Summer rice is the main crop because land is submerged from July to November.

The initial attack is by immigrant macropterous insects, which produce both macropterous and brachypterous forms, during late February and March. Hopperburn is noticed in April. The pest disappears in mid-May, at the time of rice harvest. All the high yielding photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties are attacked. But some local rice varieties of lower yield potential that are transplanted earlier escape damage.

Populations of leafhoppers and planthoppers in Egypt from 1973 to 1975, as indicated by sweep-net samples

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Samples of leafhoppers and planthoppers were taken weekly with a sweep net (1 00 double strokes/sample) throughout the April to November rice-growing seasons from 1973 to 1975 at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt. Eight cicadellid species, six delphacids, and only one cixiid were found. But two dominant species were caught in great numbers - *Balclutha hortensis* and *Sogatella vibix*. Next in abundance were *Nephotettix modulatus* and *Sogatella furcifera* (see table).

The number of leafhoppers and planthoppers increased gradually from year to year. In the three successive seasons of 1973, 1974, and 1975, cicadellids averaged 44.5, 258.6, and 929.5 insects/100 strokes, respectively; delphacids, 17.3, 271.4, and 623.1/100 strokes. In 1973, populations of most

cicadellids peaked in July and August; in 1974 and 1975, they peaked in October and November. Populations of all the delphacid species, however, peaked

in October and November in the 3 sampling years.

The average sex ratio of various species from 1973 to 1975 was near equality

Population density and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers in sweep-net samples taken weekly throughout the rice-growing season (Apr.–Nov.) at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt, 1973 to 1975.

Family and species	Mean no./100 strokes			Peak no./100 strokes ^a			Males (av %)
	1973	1974	1975	1973	1974	1975	
FAMILY CICADELLIDAE							
<i>Balclutha hortensis</i>	18.7	238.7	875.4	32.8	807.0	2955.2	46.3
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i>	6.3	3.2	42.0	14.4	13.8	166.4	54.1
<i>Cicadulina bipunctella</i>							
<i>zeae</i>	9.5	14.7	6.5	19.5	43.3	19.3	46.8
<i>Empoasca decipiens</i>	3.6	0.8	2.8	10.3	3.0	13.8	43.7
<i>Macrostelus sexnotatus</i>	5.5	0.7	1.0	16.0	2.0	3.8	28.7
<i>Exitianus taeniaceps</i>	0.9	0.5	1.3	2.8	1.5	7.3	62.8
<i>Recilia schmidtgeni</i>	0.0	0.0	0.6	—	—	2.7	—
<i>Neoliturus haematoceps</i>	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	—
Total	44.5	258.6	929.5	86.0	853.0	3136.8	—
FAMILY DELPHACIDAE							
<i>Sogatella vibix</i>	12.8	250.0	593.5	24.0	1400.0	2507.2	54.5
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	3.1	19.3	26.6	9.5	116.0	124.4	55.2
<i>Toya nigeriensis</i>	0.9	0.8	2.0	5.0	4.0	5.3	47.9
<i>Falctoya aglauros</i>	0.4	1.3	0.8	3.0	6.0	2.0	75.4
<i>Matutinus iphias</i>	0.0	0.1	0.2	—	—	—	—
<i>Dopidocephala elegans</i>	0.0	0.0	0.2	—	—	—	—
Total	17.3	271.4	623.1	41.5	1526.0	2638.0	—
FAMILY CIXIIDAE							
<i>Oliarus frontalis</i>	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	2.0	3.0	75.0

^aMonthly average.